

Place of The Media in Intercultural Communication

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Abstract

The article attaches particular importance to the cultural integration of the media, and the essence of this process is extremely ambiguous. To solve the problem of integrated culture, in order to understand the spread of the same cultural models around the world, the openness of borders to cultural influence and growing cultural communication should talk about the process of globalization of modern culture.

Keywords: intercultural communication, mass information, culture, intercultural dialogue, stereotype, common cultural space, intercultural communication, country of peace, type of culture, economic development,

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The social, political and economic changes that have taken place in recent years, as well as the rapid development of communication and information, have led more and more people to overcome cultural barriers and interact easily with other cultures. In this regard, the reference to the problems of intercultural interaction and intercultural communication is a particularly important and interesting issue. It allows you to see the difference in mechanisms among representatives of different cultures, trying to establish the causes and determine your attitude to new trends in the formation of a single cultural space. Intercultural communication is studied at an interdisciplinary level within the framework of sciences such as linguistics, cultural studies, psychology, sociology, ethnology, and so on, each science uses its own approach to consideration and analysis. Knowledge of the language of another cultural environment is necessary, but not enough for the participants to adequately understand the communication act. In addition, intercultural communication implies "not only differences between the two languages, but also differences in the use of the same language" [1, p. 25].

Currently, based on the studies of E. Hall, E. Sepir and B. Wharf, F. Boas and his followers (A. Cardiner, R. Benedict, M. Meade), some patterns of intercultural communication can be identified: 1) culture is impossible without the process of communication; 2) culture influences human behavior; 3) language and culture are interconnected, namely, the specificity of speech communication depends on the peculiarities of cultures represented by communicants; 4) the sender and the recipient of the message belong to different cultures, which makes it possible to understand each other's cultural differences; 5) intercultural communication is based on the process of symbolic interaction between individuals and groups, cultural differences that can be recognized. [7, p. 56]

In intercultural communication, different levels are distinguished. E. A. Zhukova at the micro level distinguishes several types of intercultural communication: - ethnic; - countercultures (occur between parental and daughter culture; subculture is expressed in disagreement by a daughter subculture with the values and ideals of the parent); - between social classes and groups; - between different demographic (religious, age, sex) groups; - between urban and rural residents - in the style and pace of life, general level of education, type of interpersonal relations; - regional; - business [2, p. 216]. Intercultural communication is carried out at the macro and micro levels, and is regularly influenced by various institutions and agents who are responsible for the preparation of cultural norms and the development of social roles, including the family, school, friends, various organizations, the media. 1) In what became known as the Jasmine Revolution, a sudden and explosive wave of street protests ousted the authoritarian president, Zine el-Abidine Ben Ali, who had ruled with an iron hand for 23 years. This event was called the "jasmine revolution," that is, a sudden and unstoppable wave of street protests that ousted authoritarian President Zine el-Abidine Ben Ali, who ruled the country for 23 years with an iron hand. 2) Republican Bob Brown was disgracefully beat by a... political newcomer Democrat Brian Schweitzer. Republican Bob Brown was shamefully defeated by an aspiring politician, Democrat Brian Schweitzer. The example illustrates intercultural communication at the micro level, that is, protests take place inside the country, a politician defeats the president. According to G. D. Zolina, "a modern person develops his own culture through purposeful measures to further develop the basic knowledge they received during the years of study, as well as under the influence of a continuous flow of individual elements of culture that gradually accumulate in the overall process of cultural activity. This accumulation is not the result of deliberate efforts to acquire systematic knowledge - this is not the very essence of life in our technological age,

this is due to the constant influx of a wide range of information from the environment "[3, p. 81]. The structure of consciousness, to a very large extent, is a reflection of peace, radical changes in culture. Recently, there has been a need for an integrative type of culture that will serve as a basis for the consolidation of all mankind. The result will be the convergence of national cultures and values, the strengthening of cultural, communication, civilizational ties and the achievements of science and technology, new forms of socio-political activity. Nevertheless, the formation of a new integral culture, or a single cultural space, does not mean the unification of cultural norms, ways of perceiving and understanding the world, cultural traditions, genotypes of the system. Each ethnic group, nation, society must adopt a global system of common cultural ties and interactions, which corresponds to their traditions, mentality and psychological type. The technical means of visual and sound transmission of information helped to create ideal cultural stereotypes on a global scale, which form the basis for the beginning of a new era - the metacultural period of economic development. The globalization of the main channels of communication has created cultural expansion, which is carried out through the transfer of cultural patterns at the information level, and unilaterally by aligning socio-cultural processes in all countries of the world, forming cultural stereotypes. Universal cultural stereotypes do not reflect the objective socio-cultural, political and economic conditions of our time and the historical development of the culture of countries where this information paradigm is currently created and modeled. According to S. E. Martynenko, global information stereotypes in cultural terms are an awareness of this process in almost all countries of the world. Informational cultural stereotypes, as S. E. Martynenko notes, apparently based on democratic principles, "do not contain ideological components, but integrate fundamental and historical roots, as well as peculiarities of economic development of individual countries" [4, p. 180]. Regarding the influence of the media on intercultural communication at the micro level, it should be noted that a common feature of all types is the lack of awareness of the cultural differences of its participants (except the elite). As Z. E. Pinchuk notes, it is especially "dangerous for the younger generation when the emotional sphere develops on the basis of a sense of satisfaction or dissatisfaction" [5, p. 31]. Thus, gradually surrounding society and culture are the only possible and existing world by which it identifies itself. In human consciousness, under the influence of mass culture, a certain picture of the world is formed. As a result of the impossibility of implementing some ideas, a feeling of inferiority may arise in relation to their own culture: loss of identity with their own culture, lack of identification with the majority culture; loneliness (failure); violation of role expectations and self-identification; anxiety turns into anger and disgust after awareness of cultural differences, and as a result, anorexia mortality in adolescents, alcoholism, drug addiction, frequent cases of reclusion, but this is nothing more than signs of acculturation and cultural shock. The source of cultural conflicts in our society in the near future will be an increase in social differentiation and cultural exclusion. For many decades, Soviet culture was subordinate to the idea of behavioral and mental homogeneity of society, the idea of a single lifestyle for all. Cultural polymorphism today is embodied, including in various forms of life, cultivated in various social and ethnocultural groups. The lack of traditions of organizing and regulating life in new socio-professional groups, their lack of understanding of the normative nature of everyday life, a tough lifestyle of conformity, the level of style, quality of life and stratification, ignorance of these norms cause self-identification of the problems of maladaptation, psychopathology, and in the group problems of communication and consolidation in the context of cultural changes.

Knowledge and skills are important components of effective intercultural communication. Knowledge and skills must be combined with the openness and flexibility of their individual thinking and interpretations, as well as motivation, effective communication and successful relationship building. The media have a leading role to play in addressing intercultural communication and dialogue. The media should contribute to the development of intercultural dialogue and their role in that regard was growing. The media can get information, make it accessible to various cultures and peoples, which plays a huge role in shaping the personality of young people, in particular, due to the rapidly growing Internet. The Internet allows people to come into contact with each other regardless of the location of the person. Thanks to Internet technologies, people can share their views and visions, social potential. Media is the tool by which we can access intercultural dialogue. The role of the media in the global financial crisis is increasing. As Z. E. Pinchuk notes, "the media face an alternative: give a neutral comment or give a significant assessment; the need to participate actively in political and social life "[5, p. 35]. One of the main properties of the media is to create texts in accordance with stereotypes, they help to more quickly form thinking in the process of learning or using a certain genre or type of information, and through them understand the real situation. Excessive adherence to stereotypes, however, harms the understanding of other cultures. Therefore, it is necessary to learn how to manage stereotypes by emphasizing values in another culture, which we consider positive, and to the extent possible with mild humor to perceive and respond to what we feel as a negative context. The multicultural media environment should develop the ability to put itself in other cultures, and thus divide and understand the attitude towards the world. In the field of media, according to I.P. Ryabkova, "a specialist cannot afford a communicative gap in communication with various cultures, he is obliged to suppress the rejection of the point of view of another culture. This requires serious preparation - in-depth comparative analysis of life attitudes, basic beliefs, basic cultural objects of different nationalities "[6, p. 143].

Thanks to the mass media, the participation of the widest audience is possible in the modern communication process. The new cultural space - the world of words, sound and image has a huge impact on public consciousness and the nature of interaction between cultures. Today, the media occupy one of the important places in the process of intercultural communication. Thanks to the rapid development of information, people began to easily overcome cultural barriers and interact with other cultures. A new integrative culture is being formed, which is the beginning of a new era.

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